

PEDAGOGICAL BASES OF THE NEED TO TRAIN JUNIOR SPECIALISTS WORKING IN RURAL AREAS

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ABSTRACT

This article provides specific suggestions and recommendations for improving pedagogical skills, and provides guidance on how to apply these recommendations in practice

Introduction. Considering the peculiarities of the socio-economic and cultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, its differences from the development of other countries, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan IA Karimov stressed the need to pay special attention to the following:

- commitment to universal values;
- strengthening and developing the spiritual heritage of our people;
- free expression of one's potential;
- patriotism and others.

It is on the basis of these spiritual and moral qualities that the ways of future economic renewal and development of the republic are determined. To this end, the problem of unemployment can be prevented through a

radical reorganization of the work of educating young people in general secondary schools, academic lyceums, vocational colleges. Prior to independence, Uzbekistan was considered a source of raw materials for rural areas. The issue of production of world-class finished products from agricultural raw materials, thus entering the world market, is on the agenda. To this end, the influx of industry into rural areas, the establishment of small enterprises processing agricultural raw materials, the expansion of the network of weaving, sewing, consumer services enterprises is gaining momentum. It has become a requirement of the time to train young specialists from rural youth in terms of content and quality [64-68]. "... It is necessary to bring industry to rural areas, to develop it widely, to build new small and medium enterprises and to create

additional jobs, to involve the population living in remote areas. Given the population growth, to understand how important and relevant this event is? it is not difficult," he said.

Main part. We have all the necessary capabilities to serve modern science and technology to the people. The implementation of the national training program will further expand our capabilities and lay the groundwork for a clear plan in this regard. At the same time, the development of science and technology poses complex problems for society. We need to make revolutionary changes in our thinking and make it a permanent criterion of life. In addition to the traditional tasks in the training and education of workers, there should be new, specific approaches to the current situation. In particular, more efficient use of labor and production capacity, ensuring its rapid growth, the formation of entrepreneurship of people who are able to find the most rational ways to develop production has emerged as a problem of national importance.

The greater use of research results in production leads to the expansion and transformation of the potential of the productive forces, which now includes not only physically fit people, but also professionals engaged in scientific and technical work, engaged in mental work. The role of such specialists in the rural infrastructure, ie the clerk, the bank clerk - the accountant, the staff of children's institutions, health care institutions, etc., is of particular importance.

Although new small enterprises, which have been emerging rapidly in rural areas in recent years, resemble traditional

handicraft and craft enterprises, they often use modern equipment, new materials and technology. Therefore, any worker who calls himself a "master" will not be fit to work in such enterprises. For example, a comparison of such a shoemaker 10-15 years ago and a shoemaker and shoemaker, a seamstress and a fashion designer, a carpenter and a furniture maker using modern tools shows this picture.

Results and discussion. Today's weaver cannot achieve his intended purpose by using a loom inherited from his ancestors. That is why the current enterprise, although it is called a "small enterprise", is equipped with semi-automatic or fully automatic machines, the productivity of which is several tens or even hundreds of times higher than before, the use of new - chemical, synthetic materials requires knowledge.

The economy is a complex system of production, exchange, distribution and consumption of a very wide variety of products in terms of its scale. The steady growth of material production contributes not only to the increase in the welfare and culture of the population, the consumption of material goods, but also to the improvement of their housing conditions, health care, utilities, trade and other services, recreation, education, arts and sports. it should be explained to students that it creates a wide range of opportunities. Because the majority of students do not understand the essence of professions, they do not want to work in these fields after graduation. It should also be explained that these two aspects, especially material production, are related to science and education.

By explaining the ratio of population to labor, it is important to draw students' attention to the fact that in the current situation it is very important to expand the service sector, which is directly related to the productive sector, not only as a raw material but also as a finished product. In a market economy, it is necessary to ensure economic interest not only by increasing the production of raw materials, but also by turning it into a finished product, bringing it to a level of production that meets world standards in terms of quality. So, although we have been talking about cultivating diligence until now, we have meant that in any labor there is only activity, that is, action. Now we need to cultivate a combination of both mental and physical labor, that is, a love of entrepreneurial, entrepreneurial labor. "Wouldn't it be possible to revive the various professions - potters, tinsmiths, knife-makers, packers, weavers, telpaks, etc., and fill thousands of people with jobs and the market with goods?" It requires perseverance, frustration, kindness, and more importantly, responsibility. Do the same. If necessary, we will exempt smallholders from paying taxes by a special decision," said the head of our state at the time.

To live in a society, a person must be prepared for activities of a certain nature. The masses of the people have always understood this necessity. That is why it has become the duty of the people and society to bring up the younger generation in the spirit of love for work.

Different organization of labor is a means of educating a healthy, physically strong person. Typically, people who engage in physical activity have well-developed muscles, a beautiful body structure, a

healthy lung and an energetic heart, and a normal mental system. In labor, a person's sensory organs develop and improve, which is of great importance in his aesthetic upbringing and all-round perfection. The role of labor in mental development is also incomparable. The importance of labor is especially great in the implementation of a comprehensive approach to educational work. When a person is able to work to the best of his ability, he can grow up to be a person who is useful to society, who can combine spiritual, political, labor and moral education, and who can work with adults. In turn, ideological, political, moral, intellectual, aesthetic and physical education form in students a love for work and future professions, creative initiative in a market economy, the application of theoretical knowledge in practice, allowing them to acquire professional skills faster. A healthy generation is a great asset to society. This leads to the welfare of the people. The establishment of small and private enterprises is the basis of a market economy. If we do not develop such a small but effective industry, it will be difficult to achieve our goals. There is a one-sidedness in the organization of small, medium and private enterprises. They traded more and more instead of producing consumer goods as stipulated in their charters, and did not go beyond intermediating. "Only through the development of medium, small and private entrepreneurship, improving the living standards of the rural population can we achieve sustainable development of our economy, ensure the well-being of our people.

We consider it expedient to provide brief, historical information on the preparation of young people for work in the human society,

the use of young people in career choices, before embarking on the training of personnel for the newly established manufacturing enterprises. Man works to meet his vital needs such as food, clothing, and housing. From the time he began to have a conscious influence on nature, his labor activity also emerged as he saw labor as a source of satisfaction for his spiritual needs. A person who is skilled in his work will not be indifferent to what kind of work he does. Only when he is engaged in work that is beloved and useful to him, when he masters it perfectly, when he uses his intellect, when he takes a creative approach, can he work with deep spiritual satisfaction and set an example of initiative. In our society, people who work not only in terms of material interests, but also with spiritual satisfaction, such as love of their profession, lightening the burden of the people, have always been valued. It should be noted that the analysis of young people's interest in the profession plays an important role in determining the pedagogical basis for the training of junior specialists. Our research has shown that the emergence of interest in the profession among young people is diverse and that it has different developmental dynamics. The lack of stability and stability of young people's professional orientation is due, firstly, to their age, and secondly, the rapid growth of modern science and technology, the richness of information, direct observation

and impressions, the abundance of social change in society.

Conclusions. A survey of general secondary schools to determine students' career choices concluded that 59% of students had a partial or complete change in their career choices by the time they finished grade IX, 25 percent in grade X, and 15 percent in grade 11. The percentage of career choice varies.

In addition, a survey was conducted among 9th grade students to determine the level of readiness of students to choose a profession. An analysis of their responses yielded the following results: 57 percent of students did not know where to go in grade X, 20.4 percent did not know where to go after graduating from grade IX, 15 percent did not attend secondary special education, 5.4 percent did not work, and only 1.2 percent of students decided to go to vocational schools.

The results of one-on-one interviews with ninth-graders revealed that they did not know much about their careers and did not have a full understanding of their importance in training junior specialists in various specialties. To prove our point, we asked students the following questions. Students of VIII, IX, XI grades were involved in the questions, and a total of 1234 students received answers.

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